

The Effects of Pesticides on Bats in Asia

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Abstract:- The environmental services bats perform important for maintaining healthy ecosystems. Bat species are endangered due to the widespread application of chemicals, which threatens biodiversity. Examining the historical and territorial distribution of studies, the examined species and the most widely researched categories of pesticides, this investigation paper summarizes the knowledge, effect of pesticides to bats presented between March 1953 and June 2021. Studies were conducted mainly in the Pakistan. Only 7 percent of the world's species have been investigated with most of those studies focusing on insectivorous members of the Family Vespertilionidae. There has been much research on insecticides, particularly organochlorine compounds. Most studies were empirical, and little is known about how pesticides affect wild bat populations. The total amount of studies conducted remains low about the number of active substances utilized, despite advancements in techniques to identify pollutants. Little is known about how pesticides affect non-target animals and communities in the tropics. The adverse effects of pesticides particularly at sub-lethal dosages that cause chronic exposure should be studied in the future. It is significant to examine how natural organisms react to exposure to pesticide combinations in the atmosphere to determine the influence of these compounds on other food guilds.

Keywords:- Bats, pesticides, insectivorous, vespertilionidae.

I. INTRODUCTION

The expansion of agricultural usage into previously undeveloped areas and the close connection of farms to natural ecosystems, more opportunities exist for wild animals to come into touch with sprayed pesticides and be exposed to their possible hazardous effects. Foraging in agricultural areas on possibly polluted victims or immediately absorbing these harmful substances through their bodies makes bats that consume insects highly susceptible to contamination with pesticides and their harmful impacts. Immuno-toxicity, the study of tissue, digestive problems, hormonal interruption, reproduction disappointment and changed behavior are all potential long-term sub-lethal effects of being exposed to use for farming contaminants. These cumulative, near-lethal impacts threaten farmland colonies of bats and the beneficial ecological functions they offer by reducing the number of predatory insects. There has been a global decline in bat populations which has been attributed in large part to human interference. However, it is unclear what limit of a role chemicals play in these decreases, particularly in highly at-risk areas characterized by a high bat diversity and rapid agricultural growth. Initially, biologists need to establish accurate means of detecting and monitoring the consumption of environmental contaminants and the impacts on free-living bats to fill these knowledge gaps as follows,

Table 1: Effects of pesticide on bats.

Species	Pesticide	Biomarker analyzed	Country	Type of study	Reference
"Eastern Bent-wing bat"	"Glyphosate, DDT"	Exposure	Pakistan	Observational	(Brühl et al., 2023)
"Little fruit eating bat"	"Malathion"	Effect	China	Manipulative experimental	(Basham et al., 2023)
"Brazilian free tailed bat"	"Chlorpyrifos"	Effect	Sri Lanka	Manipulative experimental	(Bruinenberg et al., 2023)
"Brazilian free tailed bat"	"DDT"	Exposure	Bangladesh	Observational	(Burgar et al., 2014)
"Little fruit eating bat"	"Paraquat"	Exposure, effect	India	Manipulative experimental	(Khairy et al., 2022)

Species	Pesticide	Biomarker analyzed	Country	Type of study	Reference
"Big brown bat"	"Imidacloprid"	Exposure	Indonesia	Observational	(Oliveira et al., 2021)
"Gray bat"	"Atrazine"	Exposure	Japan	Observational	(Bouarakia et al., 2023)
"Little brown bat"	"Carbaryl"	Determination of lethal concentration on brain	Vietnam	Manipulative experimental	(Kuzukiran et al., 2021)
"Brazilian free tailed bat"	"Diazinon"	Exposure	Turkey	Natural experimental	(Alpizar et al., 2020)
"Brazilian free tailed bat, big brown bat ,little brown bat; Indian bat ,Gray bat"	"Methomyl"	Exposure	Iran	Observational	(Charbonnier et al., 2021)
"Gray bat "	"Acephate"	Exposure	Thailand	Observational	(Gao et al., 2023)
"Brazilian free tailed bat"	"Endosulfan"	Exposure	Myanmar	Observational	(Puig-Montserrat et al., 2021)
"Brazilian free tailed "bat	Fipronil "	Determination of lethal concentration	Iraq	Manipulative experimental	(Harding et al., 2023)
"Little brown bat"	" DDD, DDE, "	Exposure	Afghanistan	Observational	(Calao-Ramos et al., 2021)
"Big brown bat "	"Captan"	Determination of lethal dose	Malaysia	Manipulative experimental	(Ferreira et al., 2022)
"Little brown bat "	"Cypermethrin "	Determination of lethal dose	Yemen	Manipulative experimental	(Puig-Montserrat et al., 2021)
"Gratbat,,try colored bat; eastern red bat"	"Copper sulphate and Hepx"	Exposure	Nepal	Observational	(Hughes et al., 2021)
"Bassans 'sserotine ; greater mouse-eared bat"	"Lindane "	Exposure	Korea	Qualitative	(Russo et al., 2023)
"Big brown bat"	"Cyfluthrin "	Effect	Syria	Manipulative experimental	(Freitas et al., 2021)
"Big brown bat; silver-haired bat; eastern red bat"	"Dimethoate ,DDT,copper sulphate,"	Exposure	Jordan	Observational	(Sotero et al., 2022)
"Indian bat; northern long eared"	"Metalaxyl,lindane, methyl paration"	Exposure	Azerbaijan	Observational	(Liu et al., 2023)
"Brazilian free tailed bat"	"Methoxychlor"	Effect	UAE	Manipulative experimental	(Jiménez-Navarro et al., 2023)
"Common pipistrelle"	"Oxamyl"	Exposure	Tajikistan	Natural experimental	(Maslo et al., 2022)
"Schreiber's long fingered bat; Greater horse shoe bat."	"Fipronil , DDTs, DCB"	Exposure	Laos	Natural experimental	(Olimpi & Philpott, 2018)
"California myotis,long eared myotis; long legged myotis,big brown bat; silvered hair bat"	"Premethrin ,Atrazine "	Exposure	Gujarat	Natural experimental	(Martín et al., 2023)
"Tera's roundleaf bat"	"Ziram "	Effect	Taiwan	Manipulative experimental	(Ferreira et al., 2023)

Species	Pesticide	Biomarker analyzed	Country	Type of study	Reference
“Tera’s roundleaf bat”	“Clopyralid “	Effect	Lebanon	Manipulative experimental	(Sandoval-Herrera et al., 2023)
“Tri-colored bat; Brown long-eared bat, Natterer's bat; Daubenton's bat or the water bat Whiskered bat”	“Chlorfenapyr”	Exposure, effect	Kyrgyzstan	Observational and manipulative experimental	(Khairy et al., 2022)
“Little brown bat; Tricolored bat, Northern long eared bat,; Eastern small-footed bat”	“Dicamba “	Exposure	Oman	Observational	(Feijó et al., 2019)
“Big brown bat”	“Diuron “	Determination of dose	magnolia	Manipulative experimental	(Kannan et al., 2010)
“Serotine bat; Geoffroy bat, noctule bat ; pipist bat; Common pipistrelle; greater horse shoe bat; Vespertilio murinus”	“Fenamidone “	Exposure, effect	Armenia	Natural experimental	(Rauchenstein et al., 2022)
“Eastern bent wing bat”	“Glufosinate“	Exposure	Qatar	Exp. natural	(Montauban et al., 2021)
“Big brown bat”	“Iprodione “	Exposure	Bahrain	Exp. natural	(Mina et al., 2019)
“Common pipistrelle”	“Mirex, Diuron”	Effect	Cyprus	Manipulative experimental	(Sow et al., 2020)
“Common pipistrelle, Big brown bat, Eastern red bat “	“Omethoate “	Exposure	Timor-leste	Natural experimental	(Sritongchuay et al., 2019)
“Pteropus mariannus, common pipistrelle, Mexican free tailed bat “	“Oxadiazon “	Exposure	Bhutan	Observational	(Wu et al., 2020)

Biomarkers that indicate quick reactions to toxic exposure might help study non-lethal toxic effects in animal's access to the danger of environmental contaminants may be measured using biomarkers which are any biological endpoint (Risk to DNA, oxidative harm, or reproduction failure) when performed efficiently these reactions may reveal the extent to which a living thing is affected by pollutants and linkages between a substance's occurrence and a biological consequence. Population and community-level impacts may be difficult to evaluate when cellular and molecular indicators are utilized in isolation. Therefore, it is important to analyze remarks at various stages of biological structure (e.g., sub-individual, person level) and to contain responsive and environmentally relevant indicators at the same time to enhance the reliability and predicted ability of risk assessment in selecting harmless indicators, which entails using easily acquired materials (e.g., blood, hair, excreta etc.), is also vital for research in wild animals, especially for fragile species (Weier et al., 2019).

Endpoints with high sensitivity and specificity are recommended for precise evaluations. However, it might be challenging to identify such biomarkers. Therefore, merging indicators offers an option to improve the effectiveness of these distinct biomarkers. For instance despite their limited

accuracy, biomarkers of DNA harm, oxidative stress, and purification pathways are effective as early alert signals in pesticide exposure cases at low concentrations. The principal method of action of the toxin is often associated with the most specific biomarkers. Few categories of chemical are known to have the same impact as pesticides made from Glyphosate on the activity of enzyme cholinesterases (ChE) in the circulatory system. As a result of decline in activity, ChE serves as a standard and accurate measure of Glyphosate exposure. When doing risk analysis, it is helpful to include particular indicators. Metabolic and immunological responses on other hand are not particularly sensitive, but they have immediate impacts on the fitness of the beings which could threaten their ability to survive or reproduce (Tremlett et al., 2021).

Due to their precarious status, several animal species need to be agreeable to scientific evaluation of biomarkers moreover, remarks observed in free-living populations may be muddled by other environmental stressors and ecological interactions in laboratory experiment, where this variance may be reduced, and the sensibleness of the biomarkers to contamination can be confirmed, hence, should be used to supplement the realism of field research. This research aims to suggest a battery of non-destructive biomarkers for use in assessing the exposure of pesticides in free-ranging bats and

spiders with subsequent validation through dose-exposure tests in caged bats. We chose three commonly used indicators in vertebrates ecotoxicology—DNA damage, acetylcholinesterase (AChE) movement, and lymphocyte profiles—because they show sensitive, particular, and environmentally essential responses to contaminants. The captive's big-brown bats (*Eptesicus fuscus*) were empirically placed on an ecologically attainable dose of glyphosate, a commonly used Dichloro-Diphenyl-Trichloroethane pesticide, and their biochemical markers were compared to those of free-living *miniopterus schreibersii bassanii* (Eastern Bent –wing bat) that inhabit various levels of agricultural expansion. This method is not designed to do a traditional examination of uncontrolled and captive bats, rather, to evaluate the efficacy of a panel of biomarkers in controlled lab facility and the field (Buchweitz et al., 2018).

Moreover, we can discover knowledge gaps in the literature and prospective paths for future study by analyzing the chronological and spatial distribution of the investigations, the varieties of bats researched, and the types of pesticides examined. When mortality of bats associated with pesticide use was recorded, the research projects were categorized as qualitative. when bats were taken in and remains were identified, the examines were categorized as observational; when bats were obtained, and remains were identified and explaining variables were studied (for

example, regions, organisms, and sexual relations), the examines were categorized as naturally occurring experimental and when the researchers conducted a study performed under controlled circumstances to measure the effects of various quantities or amounts, the investigations were categorized as manipulative experimental.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Pesticide studies in bats have evolved in tandem with ecotoxicology's study of the effects of chemicals on wildlife. Acute poisoning reports most of which were accidents, the study's starting point until the conclusion of the 1980s, the majority of publications documented exposure by residues resolve, linked colony death to exposure, or calculated the amount consumed and fatal dosage. Trichloroform insecticides, particularly premethrin and related compounds were the primary pesticides investigated, Until the 1980s, when their impact on the sexual development of communities of particular raptors was identified, Dichloro-Diphenyl-Trichloroethane (DDT) were routinely employed, this led to public concern, as such the chemicals where banned or severely restricted in many countries. The peak years for publishing were the 1980s and 1990s, with subsequent decades gradually declining (Timofieieva et al., 2021).

Fig. 1: Number of studies on pesticide in bats

Insecticides of other classes (ICs) were used more heavily after DDT were banned, but their impacts on bats weren't scientifically studied using histopathological procedure, genetics, biochemical, and metabolic measurements until after 2010. Though testing techniques have been progressing for identifying pollutants in various materials and concentrations; the amount of research studies remain inadequate.

A. The researched species and locations

Most research (58%) and (25% of total studies) were conducted in many countries with great technological possibility, in Asian countries. Chiroptera is the second-largest mammalian order in terms of species diversity. About a quarter of the world's mammal species fall into this category Nearly 1120 varieties have been described, and may be found on every continent. Chiropterans play a crucial role in maintaining ecological harmony. Most species can increase in various habitats because of the

unique dietary and physical adaptations they've acquired. Micro chiropterans have the highest dietary diversity, including hematophagous, frugivorous, insectivorous, piscivorous, polliniferous, nectarivorous, and omnivorous species. Ecological functions vital to the ecosystem's equilibrium, including pest control, seed dissemination, and fertilization, were made possible by their unique variety.

Pesticides are toxic used to eliminate or control pests that threaten crops, livestock, and the environment. As a result of their usage in warding off numerous pests, illnesses, invasive plants, and parasites, they boost crop production. In a highly competitive market, chemicals becomes a necessary option for farmers. The global rise in crop production and subsequent rise in pesticide usage has endangered human and environmental health to their voracious appetites for bugs, bats help reduce the population of numerous pests that plague farms. However, ingesting pesticides is a risk for bats that forage in croplands Some scientists have linked the global reduction in bat populations to the increase of chemicals in bats' tissues due to bioaccumulation. In addition to their environmental and economic value as transmitters of seeds in natural environments and insect population controllers in agriculture, bats come in a broad diversity of species that range throughout virtually the whole earth. However, little ecotoxicological research has examined how pesticides may affect bats' growth, actions, or reproduction. The loss of bats in an area may devastate a community's ability to provide for itself nutritionally (Gorbunova et al., 2020).

Being at the top of the supply chain makes insect-eating bats more of an insecticide target. Disease vectors, including those that spread dengue, malaria, illness, and agricultural pests, are among the insects that are reduced in numbers to insectivorous bats. Removing insect-eating bats in North Asia would devastate agricultural output costing thousands of dollars; however, fruit-eating bats also play an essential role in forest preservation and restoration by spreading seeds across broad areas. They are also excellent signs of the existence and amount of chemical contamination because of their practice exclusively fruit diet.

Bats may be contaminated with pesticides in two ways :(1) Food consumption and (2) Drinking water. When subjected to pesticides, bats maybe 30 times more susceptible than rodents. Drinking contaminated water or consuming contaminated insects are also possible routes of exposure. The fat tissue, next to the liver and the brain had the most significant amount of pesticides in bats. According to some reviewed literature, 65 species across nine families have been previously the focus of herbicide research. More than 1400 species, representing 21 families, comprise this fraction of the world's species in their analysis of organic pollutants in bats, identified 62 species, most of which were exposed to OCs and PCBs. Thus, the number of species researched remains stable after more than two decades of investigation (Rodríguez-San Pedro et al., 2020).

Fig. 2: Effected bat by pesticide

About 66% (n = 47) of the species were from the Vespertilionidae family, making it the most researched family. Some members of this family eat fish, but overall it has the most prominent species diversity range and abundance of any family Despite the family's prevalence in research, just four species—big brown bat (n = 18), common pipistrelle(n = 16), little brown bat (n = 15), and Gray bat(n = 11) accounted for about half of all investigations. The most extensively researched species are those relevant to the works' circulation. These species are restricted to the United States, except common pipstrelle, whose range extends over Europe, the Middle East, and Asia.The vast majority of the animals and plants examined eat insects. Since bats in this trophic guild are more sensitive to stress and biological accumulation due to physiological and natural variables, they have been used as effective models for assessment and tracking environmental pollution.Oral pollution is more likely in these little flying creatures because of their fast metabolisms and the enormous quantities of food they must swallow Bats can consume over 100 percent of their body mass every night, while the exact amount depends on reproductive status, organisms, and the time of year Lifespan enhances the total lifetime exposure to pollutants and the total lifetime deposition of those toxins in these animals They are also an essential guild for studying the building up of these items in the food chain due to their high trophic ranking(Baroja et al., 2021).

Some of these traits, however, are shared by bats of different trophic levels, including lifespan, rate of metabolism and location in the food web. Depending on their diet, where they search, their behavior, and metabolic rate, bats from various guilds may be impacted in different ways by pesticides Table 1 show that only 15% of the participants looked into additional trophic levels. Only one research was conducted on a nectarivorous bat such as silver haired bat, and it only looked at DDT concentrations and compounds without any consequences Pesticides are toxic and have been shown to have both deadly and sub lethal consequences for insects that pollinate plants in several

regions throughout the globe, but the impacts on pollination vertebrates are still mostly ignored little fruit eating bat and California myotis bat are two of the phyllostomids studied. At the same time, the other six are pteropodids: long eared myotis bat, long legged myotis bat, silver-haired bat, greater horse shoe bat, schreiber's long-fingered bat, and Pteropus mariannus. There is little data available to evaluate the effects of pesticide contaminants on these species, despite the fact that these animals may be subjected to these chemicals in one way or another. Since fruit bats are simple to capture than insectivores and suggest direct exposure to chemicals in cultivars, they might be a valuable option for biomonitoring procedures research. No prior study has analyzed hematophagous, omnivorous, or predatory bats; hence, there is an obvious need for such an investigation (Abdulrahman et al., 2021).

Both report shows tropical areas contain the most excellent variety and abundance of species. However, they also stand for regions that have been put under heavy stress due to the widespread use of pesticides in cultivation of staple foods like cereals, coconut oil, and sugarcane. Only nine of the reviewed research took place in a tropical climate. Bat ecotoxicology studies benefit significantly from the diversity of bat species found in tropical regions (as opposed to those found in more temperate regions; see, for example.

B. Bioaccumulation

Dichloro-Diphenyl-Trichloroethane (DDT) that kills the pest and insect, which is notoriously stable and has many biological accumulation possibilities, has been the primary subject of chemical biological accumulation studies in bats. These animals retain liquid chemicals in their fatty tissue, which may have long-lasting consequences if the fat is used for other purposes. According to the literature, bats are now exposed to fewer pesticides, suggesting a shift like exposure through time. Restricting and prohibition DDT as pesticides led to a drop in their quantities, therefore their existence should be explored regardless of whether or not they are banned.

Due to the limited number of studies, more attention has to be tendered in biological accumulation of chemical residues from other classes. Research has become significant given the increased usage of these different kinds of pesticides since their widespread introduction to the market. In addition to organophosphates, Glyphosate, and carbaryl have also been used for bats. Their steady and substantial release into the environment belies their modest bioaccumulation capacity. Bat guano and tissue included traces of these compounds, which may reflect current consumption or residence in or near bat houses. Changes in remains levels have been attributed to factors such as diet, age and sex, species biological and searching habits shelter type. Lack of uniformity in the organs utilized, techniques of removal and measurement of residues, and statistical analysis make it difficult to examine meaningful comparisons across investigations (Khairy et al., 2022).

C. Pesticides

A total of 37 chemicals or chemical metabolites were identified in the bat-focused literature. Only two of them, a triazole and an organochlorine, are employed as fungicides. Insecticides may be broken down into six different groups based on the compounds in use: Dichloro-Diphenyl-Trichloroethane (DDT) (n = 22), chlorpyrifos (n = 8), atrazine (n = 7), Acephate (n = 4), Endosulfan (n = 2), and cypermethrin (n = 1). The majority of pesticides used every year fall under these categories. Although weed killers and fungal agents have surpassed the number of insecticides used, the impacts induced by insecticides are better investigated. While insecticides and herbicides have gotten more scrutiny for their impacts, pesticides are being studied less, a herbicide of the altered glycine family, is among the most commonly employed substances in the world; however, none of the evaluated research looked into the impact of pesticides on bats or documented their interaction with herbicides.

D. Insecticides containing DDT

The chemical structure of Dichloro-diphenyl-Trichloroethane (DDT) pesticide or insecticides consists of carbon, hydrogen, and chlorinated elements. They are lipophilic, chemically resistant, and determined. They can be broken down into three categories based on their molecular arrangement. Cyclodienes (aldrin, dieldrin, Diuron, oxadiazon, heptachlor, and endosulfan), and DDT-like compounds (cypermethrin, diazinon,. They all have varying effects on the CNS, stimulating it to overactivity. DDT compounds increase excitation time by interfering with potassium channels and preventing their rapid closure. Cyclodienes and DDT suppress the function of the brain by binding to and preventing the effects of the neurotransmitter gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) receptors. Between 1953 and 1990, organic pesticides were employed extensively for agricultural purposes and for managing Pest and insects that are the carriers of tropical illnesses. Soil, water, snowfall, the environment, and mammals have all been discovered to contain traces of DDT in every part of the world where these chemicals were utilized. Because of their highly harmful effects, determination, and propensity for biological accumulation and biological magnification, numerous DDT have been prohibited in several nations. Many of these chemicals are now on the Chicago Convention's list of persistent organic pollutants; pesticides, including fenamidone, endrin, omethoate, heptachlor, endosulfan, and hexachlorocyclohexanes were targeted for elimination and restriction in this treaty (Blakey et al., 2017). DDTs (70%), fipronil (50%), Metalaxyl (30%), Glufosinate (30%), hexachlorocyclohexane (24%), and parathion (25%). Organochlorine insecticides were the pesticides with the highest number of records, including 21 different kinds of compounds or substances, the most referenced of which were DDTs (DDT, DDE, and DDD).

The most common pesticide from the 1940s through the 1970s was dichloro-diphenyl-trichloroethane, (DDT). Farming was later used after its first use in eradicating fever and the spread of malaria as early as the 1970s; this pesticide was being phased out because of its damage to ecosystems and human health. All report a steady decline in its usage for the treatment of malaria, the illness, and dengue. Dieldrin was first used commercially in the 1950s and found widespread use throughout farming and pest management since this conversion occurs rapidly, it is rarely seen in treated animals. It is also a byproduct of the process called the pesticide Aldrin. Similarly, heptachlor may be converted into heptachlor-epoxide by oxidation Aldrin and the chemical are equally susceptible to the processes of living things and the environment. One of the nine isomers is a compound that makes up the technical hexachlorocyclohexane (HCH) drug (-hexachlorocyclohexane). It was one of the most widely utilized OCs following World War II because of its insecticidal qualities. Its usage remained until the middle of 2000 despite being outlawed in several nations as early as the mid-1950s. Discovered that out of 74 publications testing positive for DDT, 61 publications indicated exposure by either the detection of residues or the verification of deaths after the application of DDT. A few research studies examined the impact of metabolic processes, histopathological, and harmful parameters and only a few experimentally conducted studies identified a fatal dose.

E. The Use of Pyrethroids

Synthetic chemicals are based on the pesticide pyrethrin, which occurs naturally in the flower extract of flowers. Since the substances are volatile in the air due to their low weight, their use as insecticides in farming has been restricted. Although the first chemicals were created in the 1940s, they needed to have the photo-stability necessary for widespread usage in agriculture until the development of permethrin in 1973. Bugs immune to organic phosphates and carbohydrates were no match for pyrethroids, which led to their meteoric rise to popularity in the 1980s. In addition to being more rapidly biodegradable than older insecticides, steroid hormones exhibit lower acute toxicity to animals. They are utilized in the agricultural sector, for health purposes, and even in homes making them one of the most popular insecticide classes.

These pesticides' risk of harm and chemical makeup allows us to classify them into two distinct categories. There is no cyan group connected to the carbon in the alcohol section of type I pyrethroids like allethrin, permethrin and bifenthrin, but there is in group II steroid hormones like fenvalerate, a substance called delta and cypermethrin. Sodium channel voltage modulators are a class of neurotoxicity insecticide that, in general, causes a condition of hyperexcitation by prolonging the process of sodium channel closure (type II having a long lasting impact than type I). In addition, type II steroid hormones may block chloride channels by binding to the receptors for GABA (Peste et al., 2015).

In contrast to their high oral bioavailability, cutaneous absorption of steroid hormones is low. Despite being lipophilic, they are considered harmless since they are broken down into less harmful molecules and do not bioaccumulate. Dog fat, dolphin liver fish and both bovine and human milk have all been shown to have pyrethroid residues. Degradation of these chemicals often occurs in sediments and groundwater while durability in surroundings might vary depending on chemical structure and the surrounding conditions. Cypermethrin, a delta fenvalerate substance, is the most often identified pyrethroid in the environment and organisms, with permethrin and cyfluthrin following closely. Being exposed to these substances is related to cancer-causing potential DNA damage, endocrine changes and detrimental function to immune system. The effects and toxicity of cypermethrin, deltamethrin, and permethrin were studied in Common pipistrelle and Eastern bent-wing bat. Alterations in glucose metabolism and oxidative stress on the liver and muscles are among the observed consequences. The traces of pesticides in Eastern bent-wing bat including oxadiazon, Buprofezine, Dimethoate, cypermethrin, and copper sulphate but does not discuss their consequences.

F. Organophosphates and carbamates

Cholinergic neurotransmitter acetylcholine (ACh) is hydrolyzed by the enzyme acetylcholinesterase (AChE) which is inhibited by organophosphate insecticides and carbamates (CARs). At the junction of the neurons, the signal from the nerve is carried by acetylcholine (ACh) which breaks down at the neuron's terminal. Once the neurotransmitter has been hydrolyzed by acetylcholinesterase (AChE), the transmission of impulses is halted. The buildup of ACh in the synaptic cleft and excessive stimulation results from the inactivation of AChE because impulse transmission is not blocked. Intermediate molecules with modest rates of hydrolysis and regeneration are produced when AChE is phosphorylated by OFs or carbamylated CARs. Because carbonylated AChE may be hydrolyzed at a quicker rate than it can be phosphorylated, carbamylation is thought to be reversible. However, phosphorylated AChE has a very low hydrolysis rate, therefore its inactivation is permanent (Stahlschmidt et al., 2012).

Insecticides containing organophosphates rise in popularity in the 1970s as a replacement for OCs that had been banned or limited. The number of insecticides made with exceeds 200. They are nevertheless commonly employed today because of their inexpensive cost in comparison to newer insecticides despite being less persistent chemicals yet having greater acute toxicity than OCs. These compounds are an important class of insecticides. In 1956, a chemical called Carbaryl entered the market for use as an insecticide or pesticide. This was the most extensively used pesticide in its class but their residues can still build up in non-target animals' tissues as well as organs and remain in soils and vegetation for months. Some pesticides allow for repeated applications, allowing for either extended or discontinuous exposure. iprodione (N = 5), oxadiazon (N = 3), Methomyle (N = 3), cyfluthrin (N = 2), and metalaxyl (N = 2) were all mentioned as OFs,

whereas carbaryl (N = 2) was the sole carbamate mentioned. Sublethal outcomes caused by OFs and CARs characterized for animal species include disturbances in behavior. Studies on the effects of OFs on bats include those on the energy digestion and liver damage on the dose-response relationship for sublethal effects on behavior and temperature regulation caused by chlorine dioxide in on the measurement of residues of iprodione, oxadiazon. The only two studies that used CARs and the pesticide carbaryl that were located with a residue evaluation in eastern red bat in the United States and a report of *Eidolon helvum* toxicity in a zoo (Dimitrov et al., 2008).

III. TOXIC EFFECTS

There needs to be more data on the impact of pesticides on the number of bats since most investigations were observations, and the total amount of research classed as natural or manipulated exploratory was equal.

Chemicals such as pests may have both direct and indirect effects on bats. The vast majority of research on toxicity is subjective, reporting instances or evaluating substances. Very few researchers have attempted to diagnose free-living communities. It can be tough to identify the impact of the decline of the ecosystem services supported by this group of animals since more data is required to quantify the harm caused by pesticides in bat species. However, as is typical in the environmental toxicology of animals in nature, researchers have concentrated on chronic exposure's sublethal impacts on biological systems, reproductive performance, and performance.

Some pesticides may impair a creature's capacity to fly and sense of direction, causing weakness and coordination breakdown. While these consequences may not directly cause mortality, they may be complicated in searching for food, leave people more exposed to predators, and raise the chance of injuries due to falls.

Fig. 3: Effect of different pesticide on different species of bat

According to studies, bats' metabolic process for energy has been found to shift. Given bats' complicated metabolisms, including a fast metabolic rate, a low energy store, and extended periods of torpor and hibernation, these alterations may have dire repercussions. Increased energy consumption may lead to more time spent hunting, more encounters with predators, and fewer resources available for other vital processes like development, the regulation of temperature, and dormancy. Production of reactive oxygen

species from pesticide breakdown may lead to oxidative damage. Bats' antioxidant capacities have also been assessed as a result. Fruit bats, in particular, may withstand more significant oxidative strain because of the high levels of phytonutrients in their diet. However, after being exposed to modest concentrations by producers' suggestions, fruit bats with greater pesticide resilience demonstrated oxidant destruction of the liver, spleen, and muscles (Bayat et al., 2014). Little is known about the effects of human activities

on bat reproduction. Many pesticides are toxic because they interfere with hormones, which might affect reproduction. Remains of pesticides may be transferred through the placenta or breast milk, affecting reproductive success, especially as young organisms may be more vulnerable to these chemicals than mature ones. Furthermore, these pollutants are linked to congenital disabilities and other developmental issues when exposed to young children. Given bats' already poor reproductive ability, a drop in their success in reproducing raises concerns about the potential for rapid population decreases and sluggish population restorations.

Pesticides, like other chemical compounds, have immunotoxin impacts, and persistent exposure to these substances has been associated with a greater propensity for illness in various animal species. However, there is currently a lack of data about the impact of these factors on bats' immune responses (Kolkert et al., 2021).

Comet and micronucleus assays are often used to examine the genotoxic and mutagenic effects of pesticides. These methods have previously been used to evaluate DNA damage in bats. However, the majority of the research did not use pesticides. Subsequently, bats may be impacted by pesticide usage in reaction to shifts in prey availability and variety that may come from changes in the environment and habitat conditions brought on by widespread agricultural development. As a result of their extensive range, relative genetic equilibrium, and diversity in diet (spanning many different food groups), bats have been proposed as useful biological indicators. However, our current understanding of how they react to environmental pollution requires further development for their utility as bioindicators.

IV. CONCLUSION

Bats and pesticides have been the subject of study for almost 60 years. Bats are often used as bioindicators, but we still need for extensive research on how chemicals affect render them a feasible option. Most of these studies are conducted in the United States and other countries in the northern part of the world. Most of the data acquired focuses on the insectivorous guild, while the frugivores, nectarines, meat-eaters, and hematophagous bats. During this time frame, researchers mainly focused on DDT or organochlorine pesticides. Even though, the quantity of pesticides has increased, the amount of research assessing their effects on bats.

The long-term survival of populations and the environmental benefits they offer should be a focus of future study, and particular attention should be given to the negative damages and consequences, particularly the ones induced by long-term exposure Bats from different food guilds. Examining, evaluating and assessing the impacts through more studies to ponder how it react to pesticides specific for a clear findings. Conclusively, due to the effects that may improve in mixes, it is essential to focus on wild populations exposure to various chemicals and other toxins.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Abdulrahman, M., Gardner, A., & Yamaguchi, N. (2021). The occurrence and distribution of bats in Qatar. *Journal of Arid Environments*, 185(July 2020), 104379. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2020.104379>
- [2.] Alpízar, P., Schneider, J., & Tschapka, M. (2020). Bats and bananas: Simplified diet of the nectar-feeding bat *Glossophaga soricina* (Phyllostomidae: Glossophaginae) foraging in Costa Rican banana plantations. *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 24, e01254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2020.e01254>
- [3.] Baroja, U., Garin, I., Vallejo, N., Aihartza, J., Rebelo, H., & Goiti, U. (2021). Bats actively track and prey on grape pest populations. *Ecological Indicators*, 126, 107718. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.107718>
- [4.] Basham, E. W., Baecher, J. A., Klings, D. H., & Scheffers, B. R. (2023). Vertical stratification patterns of tropical forest vertebrates: a meta-analysis. *Biological Reviews*, 98(1), 99–114. <https://doi.org/10.1111/BRV.12896>
- [5.] Bayat, S., Geiser, F., Kristiansen, P., & Wilson, S. C. (2014). Organic contaminants in bats: Trends and new issues. *Environment International*, 63, 40–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2013.10.009>
- [6.] Blakey, R. V., Kingsford, R. T., Law, B. S., & Stoklosa, J. (2017). Floodplain habitat is disproportionately important for bats in a large river basin. *Biological Conservation*, 215(February), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2017.08.030>
- [7.] Bouarakia, O., Linden, V. M. G., Joubert, E., Weier, S. M., Grass, I., Tschamtk, T., Foord, S. H., & Taylor, P. J. (2023). Bats and birds control tortricid pest moths in South African macadamia orchards. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 352(April), 108527. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2023.108527>
- [8.] Brühl, C. A., Arias Andres, M., Echeverría-Sáenz, S., Bundschuh, M., Knäbel, A., Mena, F., Petschick, L. L., Rüpert, C., & Stehle, S. (2023). Pesticide use in banana plantations in Costa Rica – a review of environmental and human exposure, effects and potential risks. *Environment International*, 174(March), 107877. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2023.107877>
- [9.] Bruinenberg, M., van Agtmaal, M., Hoekstra, N., & van Eekeren, N. (2023). Residues of pesticides in dairy cow rations and fly treatments reduce the number of Coleoptera in dung. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 344(November 2022), 108307. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2022.108307>
- [10.] Buchweitz, J. P., Carson, K., Reboloso, S., & Lehner, A. (2018). DDT poisoning of big brown bats, *Eptesicus fuscus*, in Hamilton, Montana. *Chemosphere*, 201, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.02.152>
- [11.] Burgar, J. M., Murray, D. C., Craig, M. D., Haile, J., Houston, J., Stokes, V., & Bunce, M. (2014). Who's for dinner? High-throughput sequencing reveals bat dietary differentiation in a biodiversity hotspot where

- prey taxonomy is largely undescribed. *Molecular Ecology*, 23(15), 3605–3617. <https://doi.org/10.1111/MEC.12531>
- [12.] Calao-Ramos, C., Gaviria-Angulo, D., Marrugo-Negrete, J., Calderón-Rangel, A., Guzmán-Terán, C., Martínez-Bravo, C., & Mattar, S. (2021). Bats are an excellent sentinel model for the detection of genotoxic agents. Study in a Colombian Caribbean region. *Acta Tropica*, 224(February), 106141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actatropica.2021.106141>
- [13.] Charbonnier, Y., Papura, D., Touzot, O., Rhouy, N., Sentenac, G., & Rusch, A. (2021). Pest control services provided by bats in vineyard landscapes. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 306(October 2020), 107207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.107207>
- [14.] Dimitrov, D. T., Hallam, T. G., Rupprecht, C. E., & McCracken, G. F. (2008). Adaptive modeling of viral diseases in bats with a focus on rabies. *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, 255(1), 69–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtbi.2008.08.007>
- [15.] Feijó, A., Wang, Y., Sun, J., Li, F., Wen, Z., Ge, D., Xia, L., & Yang, Q. (2019). Research trends on bats in China: A twenty-first century review. *Mammalian Biology*, 98, 163–172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mambio.2019.09.002>
- [16.] Ferreira, D. F., Gibb, R., López-Baucells, A., Nunes, N. J., Jones, K. E., & Rocha, R. (2022). Species-specific responses to land-use change in island insectivorous bats. *Journal for Nature Conservation*, 67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2022.126177>
- [17.] Ferreira, D. F., Jarrett, C., Wandji, A. C., Atagana, P. J., Rebelo, H., Maas, B., & Powell, L. L. (2023). Birds and bats enhance yields in Afrotropical cacao agroforests only under high tree-level shade cover. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 345(March 2022), 108325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2022.108325>
- [18.] Freitas, R. M. P., Linhares, B. S., Oliveira, J. M., Leite, J. P. V., da Matta, S. L. P., Gonçalves, R. V., & Freitas, M. B. (2021). Tebuconazole-induced toxicity and the protective effect of *Ficus carica* extract in Neotropical fruit-eating bats. *Chemosphere*, 275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.129985>
- [19.] Gao, H., Xiang, Z., He, J., Luo, B., Wang, W., Deng, Y., Yang, R., Zhou, W., Zhou, D., Jiang, Y., & Feng, J. (2023). Using expert knowledge to identify key threats and conservation strategies for wildlife: A case study with bats in China. *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 41, e02364. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2022.e02364>
- [20.] Gorbunova, V., Seluanov, A., & Kennedy, B. K. (2020). The World Goes Bats: Living Longer and Tolerating Viruses. *Cell Metabolism*, 32(1), 31–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2020.06.013>
- [21.] Harding, C., Larsen, B. B., Otto, H. W., Potticary, A. L., Kraberger, S., Custer, J. M., Suazo, C., Upham, N. S., Worobey, M., Van Doorslaer, K., & Varsani, A. (2023). Diverse DNA virus genomes identified in fecal samples of Mexican free-tailed bats (*Tadarida brasiliensis*) captured in Chiricahua Mountains of southeast Arizona (USA). *Virology*, 580(November 2022), 98–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.virol.2023.02.004>
- [22.] Hughes, M. J., Braun de Torrez, E. C., & Ober, H. K. (2021). Big bats binge bad bugs: Variation in crop pest consumption by common bat species. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 314(February), 107414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107414>
- [23.] Jiménez-Navarro, G., Rodríguez-Pérez, J., Melguizo-Ruiz, N., Silva, B., Vasconcelos, S., Beja, P., Moreira, F., Morgado, R., Barreiro, S., & Herrera, J. M. (2023). Disentangling the seasonal effects of agricultural intensification on birds and bats in Mediterranean olive groves. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 343(November 2022), 108280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2022.108280>
- [24.] Kannan, K., Yun, S. H., Rudd, R. J., & Behr, M. (2010). High concentrations of persistent organic pollutants including PCBs, DDT, PBDEs and PFOS in little brown bats with white-nose syndrome in New York, USA. *Chemosphere*, 80(6), 613–618. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2010.04.060>
- [25.] Khairy, S., Shaban, M., Negm, A. M., Eldeen, O. W., & Ramadan, E. M. (2022). Drainage water reuse strategies: Case of El-Bats drain, Fayoum Governorate, Egypt. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, 13(5), 101681. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2021.101681>
- [26.] Kolkert, H., Smith, R., Rader, R., & Reid, N. (2021). Insectivorous bats provide significant economic value to the Australian cotton industry. *Ecosystem Services*, 49(March), 101280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2021.101280>
- [27.] Kuzukiran, O., Simsek, I., Yorulmaz, T., Yurdakok-Dikmen, B., Ozkan, O., & Filazi, A. (2021). Multiresidues of environmental contaminants in bats from Turkey. *Chemosphere*, 282(March), 131022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.131022>
- [28.] Liu, Y., Si, M., Huang, Z., Feng, J., & Jiang, T. (2023). Bats are sentinels for invasive pest surveillance based on DNA metabarcoding. *Ecological Indicators*, 152(May), 110354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2023.110354>
- [29.] Martín, J., Gonkowski, S., Kortas, A., Sobiech, P., Rytel, L., Santos, J. L., Aparicio, I., & Alonso, E. (2023). Multiclass method to determine emerging pollutants in bats using a non-invasive approach based on guano matrix. *Microchemical Journal*, 188(February), 108486. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2023.108486>
- [30.] Maslo, B., Mau, R. L., Kerwin, K., McDonough, R., McHale, E., & Foster, J. T. (2022). Bats provide a critical ecosystem service by consuming a large diversity of agricultural pest insects. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 324(June 2021), 107722. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107722>
- [31.] Mina, R., Alves, J., Alves da Silva, A., Natal-da-Luz, T., Cabral, J. A., Barros, P., Topping, C. J., & Sousa, J. P. (2019). Wing membrane and fur samples as reliable biological matrices to measure

- bioaccumulation of metals and metalloids in bats. *Environmental Pollution*, 253, 199–206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2019.06.123>
- [32.] Montauban, C., Mas, M., Wangenstein, O. S., Sarto i Monteys, V., Fornós, D. G., Mola, X. F., & López-Baucells, A. (2021). Bats as natural samplers: First record of the invasive pest rice water weevil *Lissorhoptrus oryzophilus* in the Iberian Peninsula. *Crop Protection*, 141(October 2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2020.105427>
- [33.] Olimpí, E. M., & Philpott, S. M. (2018). Agroecological farming practices promote bats. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 265(April), 282–291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2018.06.008>
- [34.] Oliveira, J. M. de, Lima, G. D. de A., Destro, A. L. F., Condessa, S., Zuanon, J. A. S., Freitas, M. B., & Oliveira, L. L. de. (2021). Short-term intake of deltamethrin-contaminated fruit, even at low concentrations, induces testicular damage in fruit-eating bats (*Artibeus lituratus*). *Chemosphere*, 278, 130423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.130423>
- [35.] Peste, F., Paula, A., da Silva, L. P., Bernardino, J., Pereira, P., Mascarenhas, M., Costa, H., Vieira, J., Bastos, C., Fonseca, C., & Pereira, M. J. R. (2015). How to mitigate impacts of wind farms on bats? A review of potential conservation measures in the European context. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 51(2015), 10–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ear.2014.11.001>
- [36.] Puig-Montserrat, X., Mas, M., Flaquer, C., Tuneu-Corral, C., & López-Baucells, A. (2021). Benefits of organic olive farming for the conservation of gleaning bats. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 313(February). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107361>
- [37.] Rauchenstein, K., Ecker, K., Bader, E., Ginzler, C., Düggelein, C., Bontadina, F., & Obrist, M. K. (2022). LiDAR metrics predict suitable forest foraging areas of endangered Mouse-eared bats (*Myotis myotis*). *Forest Ecology and Management*, 515(March), 120210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2022.120210>
- [38.] Rodríguez-San Pedro, A., Allendes, J. L., Beltrán, C. A., Chaperon, P. N., Saldarriaga-Córdoba, M. M., Silva, A. X., & Grez, A. A. (2020). Quantifying ecological and economic value of pest control services provided by bats in a vineyard landscape of central Chile. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 302(June), 107063. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.107063>
- [39.] Russo, D., Mäenurm, A., Martinoli, A., Zotti, M., & Cistrone, L. (2023). Forest islands in farmland provide vital roost trees year-round for giant and common noctule bats: Management implications. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 540(April). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2023.121053>
- [40.] Sandoval-Herrera, N., Castillo, J. P., Ching, M. E. A., Herrera M., L. G., Faure, P. A., & Welch, K. (2023). Non-destructive methods to assess pesticide exposure in free-living bats. *Science of The Total Environment*, 870, 162011. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.162011>
- [41.] Sotero, D. F., Benvindo-Souza, M., Pereira de Freitas, R., & de Melo e Silva, D. (2022). Bats and pollution: Genetic approaches in ecotoxicology. *Chemosphere*, 307(P2), 135934. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.135934>
- [42.] Sow, A., Seye, D., Faye, E., Benoit, L., Galan, M., Haran, J., & Brévault, T. (2020). Birds and bats contribute to natural regulation of the millet head miner in tree-crop agroforestry systems. *Crop Protection*, 132(March). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2020.105127>
- [43.] Sritongchuay, T., Hughes, A. C., & Bumrungsri, S. (2019). The role of bats in pollination networks is influenced by landscape structure. *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 20, e00702. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2019.e00702>
- [44.] Stahlschmidt, P., Pätzold, A., Ressler, L., Schulz, R., & Brühl, C. A. (2012). Constructed wetlands support bats in agricultural landscapes. *Basic and Applied Ecology*, 13(2), 196–203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baae.2012.02.001>
- [45.] Timofieieva, O., Swiergosz-Kowalewska, R., Laskowski, R., & Vlaschenko, A. (2021). Wing membrane and Fur as indicators of metal exposure and contamination of internal tissues in bats. *Environmental Pollution*, 276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.116703>
- [46.] Tremlett, C. J., Peh, K. S. H., Zamora-Gutierrez, V., & Schaafsma, M. (2021). Value and benefit distribution of pollination services provided by bats in the production of cactus fruits in central Mexico. *Ecosystem Services*, 47(October 2019), 101197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2020.101197>
- [47.] Weier, S. M., Moodley, Y., Fraser, M. F., Linden, V. M. G., Grass, I., Tscharrntke, T., & Taylor, P. J. (2019). Insect pest consumption by bats in macadamia orchards established by molecular diet analyses. *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 18, e00626. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2019.e00626>
- [48.] Wu, C. H., Lin, C. L., Wang, S. E., & Lu, C. W. (2020). Effects of imidacloprid, a neonicotinoid insecticide, on the echolocation system of insectivorous bats. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, 163(October 2019), 94–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pestbp.2019.10.010>